

Synthesis of Substituted α -Bromo- α -formylacetophenones and Substituted Phenacyl Bromides

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Bromo-oxymethylene ketones of 2,5-dimethoxy-, 2-methoxy-5-methyl-, 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-, 2,4-dimethoxy-, and 2-methoxy-acetophenones have been prepared and subjected to acid hydrolysis with the object of obtaining the corresponding phenacyl bromides. Attempts have also been made to prepare these phenacyl bromides by bromination of the corresponding substituted acetophenone by cupric bromide in dioxane.

α -Bromo- α -formyl ketones (bromo-oxymethylene ketones) have been obtained by bromination of the oxymethylene ketones either in glacial acetic acid¹ or in dry ether². The bromo compounds have also been obtained by bromination of the sodium salt³ or of the copper chelate compound⁴ of the oxymethylene ketone in an inert solvent like dry carbon tetrachloride. The copper chelate method is reported to furnish a better and purer yield⁴. Following this procedure, we have synthesised 2,5-dimethoxy-(I), 2-methoxy-5-methyl-(II), 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-(III), 2,4-dimethoxy-(IV), and 2-methoxy- α -bromo- α -formylacetophenone (V).

(I) $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{OMe}$; $\text{R}''=\text{H}$.

(II) $\text{R}=\text{OMe}$; $\text{R}'=\text{Me}$; $\text{R}''=\text{H}$.

(III) $\text{R}=\text{OH}$; $\text{R}'=\text{OMe}$; $\text{R}''=\text{H}$.

(IV) $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{OMe}$; $\text{R}''=\text{H}$.

(V) $\text{R}=\text{OMe}$; $\text{R}'=\text{R}''=\text{H}$.

(VI) $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{OMe}$; $\text{R}''=\text{H}$.

(VII) $\text{R}=\text{OMe}$; $\text{R}'=\text{H}$; $\text{R}''=\text{Me}$.

(VIII) $\text{R}=\text{OH}$; $\text{R}'=\text{H}$; $\text{R}''=\text{OMe}$.

(IX) $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{OMe}$; $\text{R}''=\text{H}$.

(X) $\text{R}=\text{OMe}$; $\text{R}'=\text{R}''=\text{H}$.

Direct bromination of acetophenones having activating groups such as -OH leads to nuclear bromination. Thus when *o*-hydroxyacetophenone is brominated with reagents like bromine in acetic acid, ether, carbon tetrachloride, dioxane⁵ or aqueous acetic acid⁶

1. Wislizenus and Ruthing, *Annalen*, 1912, 379, 260.

2. Deshpande *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1946, 23, 43; 1949, 26, 55.

3. Bokadia *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, 33, 363.

4. Garg and Bokadia, *ibid.*, 1957, 34, 286.

5. Dombrovskii, *Russ. Chem. Rev.*, 1961, 30, 635.

6. Marathey, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 22B, 40.

or with *N*-bromosuccinimide or pyridino-bromine complex⁷, nuclear bromination takes place.

Chatterjee and Mehrotra⁸ effected the hydrolysis of some α -bromo- α -formylacetophenones to the corresponding phenacyl bromides. Following this procedure with some modifications, we have hydrolysed 2,5-dimethoxy- and 2-methoxy-5-methyl- α -bromo- α -formylacetophenones to furnish the corresponding phenacyl bromides. All our attempts to hydrolyse 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-, 2,4-dimethoxy-, and 2-methoxy- α -bromo- α -formylacetophenones, however, failed.

Doifide and Marathe⁹ brominated substituted acetophenones in the α -position by treating them with cupric bromide in dioxane. By this procedure, the bromination of 2-methoxy-5-methylacetophenone was effected in the α -position, whereas bromination of 2,4-dimethoxyacetophenone afforded 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenacyl bromide (VIII). Thus this reagent (CuBr₂ in dioxane) at times effects demethylation and this is the first recorded case of this type. Bromination in other cases resulted in intractable gummy products.

EXPERIMENTAL

2,5-Dimethoxy- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone (I).— A mixture of 2,5 dimethoxyacetophenone (9.0 g.), prepared from hydroquinone dimethyl ether¹⁰ by the Friedel-Crafts reaction, and ethyl formate (5 ml) was gradually added in small instalments with constant shaking to a well-cooled suspension of sodium dust (1.4 g.) in dry ether (100 ml). The contents were kept at the room temperature for 24 hr. with occasional shaking. The sodium salt was filtered at the pump, washed with dry ether, and dried. It was then added in small instalments with shaking to an excess of saturated solution of copper acetate. The precipitated copper chelate compound was filtered, washed with water, and dried. The purified copper salt melts at 140°. (Found: Cu, 12.8. C₂₂H₂₂O₈ Cu requires Cu, 13.3%).

The copper chelate compound (9.0 g.) was suspended in dry CCl₄ (20 ml) and bromine (6.4 g.), dissolved in the same solvent (20 ml), was added gradually with shaking to the suspension, kept at ice temperature. Cupric bromide was filtered and the solvent was removed on a water bath. The crude product (6.3 g.) was crystallised from ethanol as shining crystals, m.p. 116°. (Found: Br, 29.4. C₁₁H₁₁O₄ Br requires Br, 27.8%).

2-Methoxy-5-methyl- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone (II).— 2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone, prepared from *p*-cresyl acetate¹¹, was methylated. The methoxy compound (8.2 g.) was formylated as described above and its copper chelate compound after purification melted at 110°. (Found: Cu, 13.7. C₂₂H₂₄O₆Cu requires Cu, 14.2%).

The copper chelate compound (8.5 g.) was brominated to yield a pale yellow solid (4.5g.). It was recrystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 80°. (Found: Br, 30.1. C₁₁H₁₁O₃Br requires Br, 29.5%).

7. Ghisya and Marathe, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 28.

8. This *Journal*, 1962, 39, 599.

9. Doifide and Marathe, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 2025.

10. Robinson and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 393.

11. Anwers and Anschutz, *Ber.*, 1921, 54B, 1649.

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone (III).—2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (8.3 g.), prepared from resacetophenone¹², was formylated in the usual way. The copper chelate compound was then prepared and purified. It decomposed above 200°. (Found: Cu, 13.5. $C_{10}H_{10}O_6Cu$ requires Cu, 14.1%).

The copper chelate compound (8.5 g.), suspended in CCl_4 (20 ml), was treated with bromine (8.4 g.). The product (5.4 g.) after removing the solvent was recrystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 164°. (Found: Br, 29.9. $C_{10}H_8O_4Br$ requires Br, 29.3%).

2,4-Dimethoxy- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone (IV).—Resacetophenone was methylated to form 2,4-dimethoxyacetophenone (9 g.) and then the product was formylated. The copper chelate compound was prepared and purified in the usual way; m.p. 183°. (Found: Cu, 13.1. $C_{12}H_{12}O_6Cu$ requires Cu, 13.3%).

The copper chelate compound (9 g.) was brominated and after removal of the solvent, a pale yellow solid (5.8 g.) was obtained. It was recrystallised from ethanol as shining crystals, m.p. 148°. (Found: Br, 28.3. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4Br$ requires Br, 27.8%).

2-Methoxy- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone (IV).—*o*-Hydroxyacetophenone¹³ was prepared and methylated. The methylated product (7.5 g.) was formylated and copper chelate compound was then prepared and purified; m.p. 169°. (Found: Cu, 14.7. $C_{10}H_{10}O_6Cu$ requires Cu, 15.2%).

Copper chelate compound (8 g.) was brominated in the usual way and the product (5 g.) was recrystallised from ethanol as colorless crystals, m.p. 114°. (Found: Br, 31.7. $C_{10}H_9O_5Br$ requires Br, 31.1%).

2,5-Dimethoxyphenacyl Bromide (VI): (i) *By Hydrolysis of 2,5-Dimethoxy- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone*.—The bromo-cxymethylene (3 g.) was refluxed with *N*-HCl (50 ml) for about 2 hr. The reaction mixture was extracted with ether and the product (2 g.) was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 89° (lit.⁸ m.p. 91°). (Found: Br, 31.4. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{11}O_3Br$: Br, 30.9%).

(ii). *Attempted Bromination of 2,5-Dimethoxyacetophenone by Cupric Bromide Method*.—2,5-Dimethoxyacetophenone (3.6 g.) and cupric bromide (9 g.) in dioxane (100 ml) were refluxed for 3 hr. in an oil bath. The white cuprous bromide was filtered and dioxane removed under reduced pressure when a viscous black liquid was obtained. Attempts to crystallise the pure product failed.

2-Methoxy-5-methylphenacyl Bromide (VII).—(i). 2-Methoxy-5-methyl- α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone (3 g.) was hydrolysed with *N*-HCl (50 ml). The product (2.4 g.) was purified by repeated crystallisations from ethanol to afford colorless needles, m.p. 97°. (Found: Br, 33.6. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2Br$ requires Br, 32.9%).

(ii) 2-Methoxy-5-methylacetophenone (3.3 g.) was brominated with cupric bromide (9 g.) in dioxane. The product (2.3 g.) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 91°. (The melting point of this did not change even after repeated crystallisation. But its mixed m.p. with previous sample was 97°).

12. Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 280.

13. Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", p. 676.

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenacyl Bromide (VIII).—(i). Hydrolysis of the bromo-oxymethylene by using HCl of different strengths under varied conditions did not succeed.

(ii). *Bromination of 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone with Cupric Bromide*.—The product as reported earlier⁹ was obtained; m.p. 161°.

2,4-Dimethoxyphenacyl Bromide (IX).—Attempted preparation by hydrolysis of 2,4-dimethoxy α -formyl- α -bromo-acetophenone did not succeed. The original substance was recovered (m.p. and mixed m.p. 148°).

Bromination of 2,4-Dimethoxyacetophenone by Cupric Bromide: 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenacyl Bromide.—2,4-Dimethoxyacetophenone (3.6 g.) and cupric bromide (9 g.) in dioxane (100 ml) were refluxed for 3 hr. on an oil bath. The white cuprous bromide was filtered and dioxane removed under reduced pressure. A thick black mass was left which was extracted with ether. The product (2.5 g.) after repeated crystallisations from a mixture of light petroleum and benzene melted at 161° (lit. m.p. of 2,4-dimethoxyphenacyl bromide, 102° and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl bromide, 161°). Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone, 161°. So demethylation at 2-position took place.

2-Methoxyphenacyl Bromide (X): (i) *Attempted Preparation by Hydrolysis of 2-Methoxy- α -formyl- α -bromo-acetophenone*.—Hydrolysis of the bromo-oxymethylene did not take place and the original substance was recovered.

(ii). *Attempted Bromination of 2-Methoxyacetophenone by Cupric Bromide*.—The product obtained after refluxing with cupric bromide could not be crystallised.